

Supporting Information

Solvent-molecule interaction induced gating of charge transport through single-molecule junctions

Zheng Tang,^{‡a} Songjun Hou,^{‡b} Qingqing Wu,^{‡b} Zhibing Tan,^{‡a} Jueting Zheng,^a Ruihao Li,^a Junyang Liu,^a Yang Yang,^a Hatef Sadeghi,^b Jia Shi,^a Iain Grace,^b Colin J. Lambert,^{b,*} and Wenjing Hong^{a,*}

^aState Key Laboratory of Physical Chemistry of Solid Surfaces, College of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Collaborative Innovation Center of Chemistry for Energy Materials (iChEM), Xiamen University, Xiamen 361005, China

^bDepartment of Physics, Lancaster University, Lancaster LA1 4YB, United Kingdom

*To whom correspondence should be sent: whong@xmu.edu.cn and c.lambert@lancaster.ac.uk

[‡]These authors contributed equally to this work.

Table of Contents :

1. Experimental Results	S2
1.1. Solvent dependent background noise	S2
1.2. Conductance histograms of OPE-SMe in mixed solvents	S2
1.3. Control Experiments	S5
1.4. UV/vis absorptions	S6
2. Theory: Computational Methods	S7
2.1. The influence of anchor on the solvent gating effect for OPE, OAE and ODT	S7
2.2. How to generate many configurations for OPE-SMe with one THF or ACN molecule	S10

1. Experimental Results

1.1. Solvent dependent background noise

Figure S1. 1D conductance histograms of pure TMB (blue), THF (red) and ACN (yellow).

As shown in Figure S1, the higher permittivity of the solvent would result in higher tunneling leakage current through solvent and shows higher background noise. Therefore, mixing TMB with lower permittivity and volatility can reduce the background noise and reduce the change of solvent composition during the measurement.

1.2. Conductance histograms of OPE-SMe in mixed solvents

Figure S2. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvents (THF and TMB v:v = 1:4). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S3. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvents (THF and TMB v:v = 2:3). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S4. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (THF and TMB v:v = 3:2). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S5. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (THF and TMB v:v = 4:1). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S6. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (ACN and TMB v:v = 1:4). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S7. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (ACN and TMB v:v = 2:3). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S8. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (ACN and TMB v:v = 3:2). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S9. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in mixed solvent (ACN and TMB v:v = 4:1). Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S10. (a) 1D conductance histogram and (b) 2D conductance histogram of OPE-SMe in pure ACN. Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

1.3. Control Experiments

Figure S11. (a) 2D conductance-displacement histograms for OPE-SAc in TMB, (b) THF, and (c) ACN. Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S12. (a) 2D conductance-displacement histograms for OAE in TMB, (b) THF, and (c) ACN. Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S13. (a) 2D conductance-displacement histograms for ODT in TMB, (b) THF, and (c) ACN. Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

Figure S14. (a) 2D conductance-displacement histograms for 1,3Az in TMB, (b) THF, and (c) ACN. Inset: The relative displacement distribution histograms.

1.4. UV/vis absorptions

Figure S15. UV-vis absorptions of OPE-SMe (1.0×10^{-4} mol/L) measured in TMB (blue), THF (red), and ACN (yellow) at room temperature.

To further understand the solvent-molecule interaction, the UV-vis absorptions of OPE-SMe in TMB, THF and ACN are measured at room temperature. The highly consistency of the absorption spectrums indicate that the width of molecular HOMO-LUMO gap do not show a significant solvent induced shift.

2. Theory: Computational Methods

Geometrical optimizations were performed by using the DFT code SIESTA, with a local density approximation GGA functional), double- ζ polarized basis, a cutoff energy of 150 Ry and a 0.02 eV/Å force tolerance. To compute their electrical conductance, the molecules were each placed between pyramidal gold electrodes. For each structure, the transmission coefficient $T(E)$ describing the propagation of electrons of energy E from the left to the right electrodes was calculated using the Gollum code, which combines the mean-field Hamiltonian and overlap matrices of the DFT code SIESTA with the quantum transport theory, via the expression

$$T(E) = \text{Tr}[\Gamma_L(E)g(E)\Gamma_R(E)g^\dagger(E)] \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma_{L,R}(E) = i(\Sigma_{L,R}(E) - \Sigma_{L,R}^\dagger(E))/2$. $\Gamma_{L,R}$ determines the width of transmission resonances, $\Sigma_{L,R}(E)$ are the self-energies describing the contact between the molecule and left (L) and right (R) electrodes. While g is the retarded Green's function of the molecule in the presence of the electrodes.

2.1. The influence of anchor on the solvent gating effect for OPE, OAE and ODT

Figure S16. The conformation for OPE anchored by SMe group to two gold leads with two solvent molecules pointing different sides (a) ACN (b) TMB. The transmission spectra of OPE anchored by SMe group to two gold leads with and without solvent molecules (c) ACN (d) TMB.

Figure S17. The conformation for OAE with two solvent molecules pointing different sides (a) THF (b) ACN (c) TMB. The transmission spectra of OAE attached to two gold leads with and without solvent molecules (d) ACN (e) TMB.

Figure S18. The conformation for ODT with two solvent molecules pointing different sides (a) THF (b) ACN (c) TMB. The transmission spectra of ODT attached to two gold leads with and without solvent molecules (d) ACN (e) TMB.

Figure S19. The conformation for OPE anchored by SAc to two gold leads with two solvent molecules pointing different sides (a) THF (b) ACN. The transmission spectra of OPE anchored by SAc to two gold leads with and without solvent molecules (c) ACN.

Figure S20. The frontier molecular orbitals HOMO-2, HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO, LUMO+1, LUMO+2 and LUMO+3 of isolated molecules of OPE-SMe, OPE-SH and OAE as well as the corresponding energy eigenvalues (in eV).

Figure S21. The frontier molecular orbitals close to LUMO, HOMO and LUMO for OPE-SMe, OPE-S and OAE separately as well as the corresponding energy eigenvalues (in eV).

2.2. How to generate many configurations for OPE-SMe with one THF or ACN molecule

The initial configurations of OPE with one THF or ACN molecule are shown in Fig. S22 and S23, then 112 configurations are obtained by rotating THF (ACN) around X axis 10° each time until 360° and shifting THF (ACN) along the Z axis 0.2 \AA each time. The solvent molecule is relaxed by fixing the backbone molecule using LDA. Then they are attached to gold electrodes to get the transmission spectra.

Figure S22. The initial conformation of OPE with one THF molecule.

Figure S23. The initial conformation of OPE with one ACN molecule.